

The use of LLC Lignohumat preparations containing humic substances in agriculture

Kondratiev V.M.

Lignohumat LLC, Saint Petersburg, Russia, vk@lignohumate.ru

Keywords: spring wheat, herbicidal stress, yield, lignohumate

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17343561

The intensive nature of agricultural activity involves the use of a larger number of chemicals – mineral fertilizers, pesticides (herbicides, insecticides, fungicides). Herbicides have the greatest phytotoxicity for cultivated plants. An indirect way to assess the herbicide load is the volume of herbicide production. In Russia, from 2016 to 2022, the volume of herbicide production increased from 49.9 to 126.0 thousand tons [1], which indicates a 2.5-fold increase in the herbicide burden on agricultural crops. Such growth leads to inhibition of the metabolism of agricultural plants, inhibition of development. In this regard, there is a need to remove plants from the "herbicide pit". One of the ways to overcome herbicidal stress is the use of preparations containing humic substances. Due to the large number of functional groups, humic substances have a number of properties, one of which is the formation of complexes with molecules of the active substance of herbicides [2]. The most technologically advanced method of obtaining humic substances is the processing of lignin-containing plant raw materials obtained during wood processing. NPO RET LLC has developed and successfully uses a waste-free technology for processing plant raw materials (lignosulfonate) by the method of oxidative-hydrolytic degradation, which makes it possible to obtain high-quality liquid and powdered humic preparations sold by LIGNOHUMAT LLC.

The preparations of LIGNOHUMAT LLC are annually tested in the fields of agricultural producers, where they are used together in tank mixtures with pesticides. The accounting of yields in the tests was carried out according to generally accepted methods. The obtained yield data was mathematically processed by the method of variance analysis. In 2021, the tests were carried out on crops of spring wheat of the Ekada variety on the farm of Ural-Tau Agricultural Enterprise LLC. During the growing season, foliar treatment was carried out, according to the technology of the farm, with the herbicide Trisil (Tifensulfuron-methyl 300 g/kg+Tribenuron-methyl 300 g/kg+Florasulam 100 g/kg). In the experimental version, the preparation Lignohumate BM was added to the tank mixture at a dose of 1 l/ha. The yield in the control variant was 20.5 c/ha, in the experimental variant – 22.7 c/ha (HCP0.05 = 1.1 c/ha). In 2023, tests were carried out in the fields of CJSC Plemzavod Yubileyny on spring wheat of the Licamero variety. During the growing season, foliar treatments were carried out with the following pesticides, according to the technology of the farm: Absolute+Tribune SP, Zeppelin CE+Title 390+AgroPrim ME. In the experimental version, Argolan Aqua was added to the tank mixture at a dose of 0.5 l/ha. The yield in the control variant was 35.2 c/ha, in the experimental variant – 39.0 c/ha (HCP0.05 = 1.8 c/ha). An increase in the yield of spring wheat by 2.2 and 3.8 c/ha, respectively, compared with the control, indicates the overcoming of herbicidal stress.

Based on the results of the tests, it can be concluded that the humic substances contained in Lignohumate preparations have a stimulating effect and make it possible for cultivated plants to overcome herbicidal stress, but the issue of the mutual influence of herbicides and humic substances on weeds remains unclear.

References

1. Agriculture in Russia: [electronic resource]. URL: https://rosstat.gov.ru/storage/mediabank/S_x_2023.pdf (date of reference: 08/01/2025).
2. Popov A. I. Humic substances: properties, structure, formation. St. Petersburg: Publishing House of St. Petersburg University, 2004. 248 p.